

HUMAN CAPITAL FLIGHT IN NIGERIA: IMPLICATIONS ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN HEALTH AND EDUCATION SECTORS

¹Secunda Chibozam Onwuharaonye (PhD), ²Awu Chima Orji (PhD), ³Akor Sunday (PhD) and ⁴Eunice Ahanotu (PhD)

^{1,2}*Department of History and International Studies Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri.*

³*Department of Political Science Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri*

⁴*Department of Music Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri*

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Abstract: *Nigeria as a country is in fervent search for development however constrained by brain drain of productive human resources. From this background, this study examined the effects of human capital flight in Nigeria's economic development with reference to health and education sectors. The methodology of the study is a qualitative design. The study revealed factors/drivers of human capital occasioned with adverse effects on social welfare and labour productivity (as key indicators of economic development) which reflects in poor clinical services, public medic facilities, inadequate health workers and consultants as there are other challenges such as failure of the government to implement recommendations for sectoral reforms, failure of the union of vice chancellors to engage the government on priority needs and, other constraining efforts. From these findings, the study advocated for effective synergy between government and industrial unions of Nigeria's professionals on welfare and conducive working environment, long term national action-plan to address the challenges of flight of professionals to other parts of the world as among other measures to mitigate human capital flight and boast economic development.*

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Introduction

Human capital flight is an interesting discourse in the international political economic relation because of its gains and losses to both foreign and domestic economies (Carl, 2007). Human capital flight is peculiar to every country but with a different dimension and scale of effects. It is observed that no economy boast of 100 percent concentration of its human resources in isolation of the motive to migrate to other economies (Omowumi, 2018). In a generic sense, Onwunyi, et al (2020) opined that migration of people has been a regular and common phenomenon of world history, whether as skilled or unskilled. In recent time, migration of skilled labour popularly known as human capital flight or brain drain is widely discussed for its larger consequences and its impacts on developing countries. The inspiration of moving from one's home country to abroad is dynamic and cannot be generalized. The reason may be that the developed foreign countries encourage better opportunity than a home country can provide. These concerns therefore underscored the strand of economic development studies related to domestic challenges.

In this vein, Andrew (2022) observed that economic development first become a major

concern after the World War II. As the era of European colonialism ended, many former colonies and other countries with low living standards came to be termed underdeveloped countries to contrast their economies with those of the developed countries which were understood to be Canada, the United States, those of the western Europe, most eastern European countries to the then Soviet Union, Japan, South Africa, Australia and New Zealand. As living standards in most poor countries began to rise in subsequent decades they were termed as the developing countries. Most importantly, the post-colonial years witnessed the height of neglect and deprivation in three successive decades which unfortunately made many skilled individuals to migrate to developed economies.

Nigeria is constantly losing highly skilled professionals in various sectors of the economy to developed countries via migration. Recently, the rate of migration of highly skilled Nigerian workers is disturbing as this has created gaps in several sectors like the oil and gas, technological industry, and the most alarming gap appears within the healthcare and education sectors (Anetoh & Onwudinjo, 2020). Hence, this recurring reality ostensibly elicits the rationale of what it represents. In a succinct sense, human capital flight (HCF), also known as

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brain drain or brain flight seen as the movement of highly skilled workers from one country to other countries in search of better standard of living, better quality of life, higher salaries, access to advanced technology and more stable political conditions (Etuk, e tal 2023).

Furthermore, Akinwale (2020) observed that human capital flight occurring in Nigeria has greatly affected economic growth and development. It was argued that human capital flight is one of the adverse realities which have over the years eroded gains of the economy (Benson, 2018). Thus, its effects are mostly felt on widespread misery and widening inequalities which undermined efforts towards improved standard of social existence and living (Etim & Samuel, 2019). In this vein, it was further remarked that economic development implies achieving sustained rates of growth of income per capita which enables a nation to expand its output at a rate faster than the growth rate of its population. In a more illustrative sense with reference to process and impact, it is also argued that economic development represents direct efforts to lower widespread and absolute poverty, increasingly inequitable income distributions, and rising unemployment. During the 1970s, economic development came to be redefined in terms of the reduction or elimination of poverty, inequality, and unemployment within the

context of a growing economy. Hence, Seers (1970) posed a basic question about the meaning of economic development: the questions to ask about a country's development are therefore, what has been happening to the economic development of a nation? He opined that if all the three of these have declined from high levels, then beyond reasonable doubt, there is economic development in the country concerned. He argues that a number of developing countries experienced a relatively high rate of per capita income during the 1980s and 2000s but showed little or no improvement or even an actual decline in employment, equality, and the real income of the bottom 40% of their population. Given the view of Seers, economic development depends on the three indicators, which are poverty, inequality and unemployment (cited in Akinwale, 2020). In a similar sense, economic development policies are designed to address challenges of lower levels of living and productivity, lower levels of human capital, higher levels of inequality and absolute poverty, higher population growth rates, greater social fractionalization, larger rural population, rapid rural-to-urban migration, lower levels of industrialization, adverse geography etc (Todaro and Smith, 2011). From the indices of socio-economic development challenges, Akanegbu and Gidigbi (2014) argued that Nigeria as a

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country for several decades and years has been grappling with enormous challenges of poverty and unemployment rates while many indigent population, which is over seventy (70) per cent of the population, were not able to meet their basic needs, faced with limited means of satisfying their wants, and ultimately, lost a sense of worthiness in the society. Similarly, Etimi (2020) indicated that the successive administrations in the country have not really showed enough political will to mitigate against problems of basic social services (portable drinking water, quality medical care, functional education) and infrastructure which are the critical variables of economic development for the purpose of improving living standard and life expectancy.

A closer cursory view of the foregoing scholarly analysis illuminate gaps in the effects of human capital flight on economic development of Nigeria. This gap underscored the rationale for this study which aims to investigate the effects of human capital flight on economic development in Nigeria.

Conceptual Analysis

Human Capital Flight

Basically, it is pertinent to examine scholarly views on what human capital represents from human capital flight. Human Capital refers to the stock of productive skills and technical

knowledge embodied in labor (Wagle, 2009). In an etymological sense, the term, “Human Capital” was expounded by Schultz (1961) to indicate that all human abilities (innate or acquired) that are valuable and can be augmented by appropriate investment. More explicitly, Bontis (1999) noted that Human Capital represents the human factor in the organization. It deals essentially on intelligence, skills and expertise that give the organization its distinctive character. The human elements of the organization are those that are capable of learning, changing, innovating and providing the creative thrust which if properly motivated can ensure the long-term survival of the organization. On a larger scale, human capital places emphasis on the indispensability of ‘Man’ in the total control and development of the world as pointed out by Aristotle (BC), ‘Man is the ultimate’. Hence, the value derived from human knowledge, skills and abilities are the reasons for the struggle by advanced nations as in the slavery and colonial dispensation to attract, retain, develop and maintain human capital to their advantages especially from Africa (Egbefo, 2014).

Similarly, Human capital is described as the total stock of knowledge, skills, competencies and innovative capabilities possessed by a country (Robinson and Florence, 2016). Shuaibu

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and Oladayo (2016) consider this approach when they affirm in their study that human capital flight has its origin from the increasing pace in the division of human labor. Shuaibu and Oludayo (2016) also follow this trail when they defined human capital as knowledge, competency, attitude and behavior possessed by an individual and further explained that a fundamental source of productivity in the world is its human capital. Fundamentally, human capital is acquired partly through education (Shahbaz et al., 2019), and it is that intangible factor that brings human intelligence, skills, abilities and competencies in the production process and allows for the provision of goods and services (Amadi and Alolote, 2019). Therefore, human capital development concerns all kinds of labor, mentoring, practices, internship and investment, such as efficient medical facilities on managing the available human capital (Oluwaseyi and Oluyemi, 2020).

In other words, human capital resonates from value of labour appropriated for growth and development. Furthermore, Adam Smith as noted defined human capital as one of the four types of fixed capital that were: (i) useful machines as instruments of the trade; (ii) buildings as the means of procuring revenue; (iii) improvements of land and (iv) human capital. It

as “the acquired and useful abilities of all the inhabitants or members of the society. The acquisition of such talents, by the maintenance of the acquirer during his education, study, or apprenticeship, always costs a real expense, which is a capital fixed and realized, as it were, in his person. Those talents, as they make a part of his fortune, so do them likewise that of the society to which he belongs. The improved dexterity of a workman may be considered in the same light as a machine or instrument of trade which facilitate and abridge labour, and which, though it costs a certain expense, repays that expense with a profit.” (Smith, 1968 cited in Okolo, 2012). In credence, human capital is the critical component of productivity and growth.

Furthermore, Human Capital is also known as the stock of skills and productive knowledge embodied in people. The yield or return to human capital investment lies in enhancing a person’s skills and earning power (private return), and in increasing overall economic efficiency through complementary application of different skills and improved economic decision-making both within and without the market economy (developmental value). Adam Smith in *Wealth of Nations* identified the improvement of workers’ skills as a fundamental source of economic progress and increasing human welfare (cited in Eatwell et al, 1996).

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These improvements are achieved not only through education and formal training, but also, through learning by doing. From an individual's perspective investment in human capital is a life-long process. Knowledge embodied in a person includes abilities for problem solving, command over relevant information, and technical, managerial, and entrepreneurial skills.

However, Wagle (2009) observed that phenomenal increase in the migration of skilled and educated professional workers in recent years, particularly from developing to developed countries causing depletion or loss of intellectual and technical personnel in the countries where the need is more acute has initiated new form of debate in recognizing human capital and its impact in the deployment process of the underdeveloped areas. Thus, this situation is appropriately contextualized as human capital flight. To this end, human capital flight is viewed as emigration of trained and talented individuals to other nations or jurisdictions. There are several arguments by many economists for and against such 'drain' and its impact in development. These arguments as observed formed the thrust of this study.

Human Capital Flight is therefore defined as the movement of highly skilled workers from one country to other countries in search for better

standard of living, better quality of life, higher salaries, access to advanced technology and more stable political conditions. Interestingly, unlike actual brain drain, human capital flight intent is not explicit. It connotes large-scale movement or migration of top flight manpower from various developing countries (mainly African countries) to developed countries notably United States of America, United Kingdom, Canada, Germany, France, Holland, New Zealand, Italy, United Arab Emirate, Australia, etc. As earlier noted, the main reason for this movement could be the quest for better opportunities (Etuk, e tal 2023). Similarly, Adewumi, e tal (2019), indicated that human capital flight simply refers to the migration of highly skilled or well-educated individuals for better opportunities. The benefits from skilled migration refer to as brain gain, and the cost is referred to brain drain. Human capital flight always involves the movement of skilled professionals from less developing countries to developed ones.

In a different perspective, Human Capital Flight is seen as a movement of highly skilled or professional people from their own country to another country where they can earn more money. The thought process of actualizing this is known as human capital flight intention. Thus, human capital flight intention refers to the

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likelihood of highly skilled workers or professionals to migrate. Human capital flight intention as the likelihood of highly trained and well experienced practitioners migrating from countries with poor conditions of service to those with better work conditions in search of greener pasture (Utile, 2008). This perspective undoubtedly elicit curiosity on what inform migration of skilled and experienced persons from their countries to other economies of the world.

In a succinct sense, Emeghara (2019) noted that the term, “brain drain”, is also known as human capital flight. It means large-scale movement or migration of top flight manpower from various developing countries (predominantly African countries) to more developed countries notably United States of America, Canada, United Kingdom, Germany, France, Italy, Holland, Newzeland and Australia. As earlier stated, the chief reason for this movement is the quest for better opportunities. Similarly, the Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English defines brain drain as a movement of highly skilled or professional people from their own country to a country where they can earn more money . With particular reference to the University system, Utile (2008) conceptualizes brain drain as the mass exodus of highly trained and well experienced academics from

countries with poor conditions of service to those with better work conditions in search of greener pasture. Brain drain is common amongst such skilled personnel as medical doctors, pharmacists, nurses, medical laboratory scientists, industrial chemists and pilots. Others are computer scientists, engineers, university lecturers, researcher stechnologists and lawyers. The term brain drain originally referred to technological workers leaving a nation. But nowadays its application or meaning has widened to include the migration of educated and professional people from one country, economic sector or field for another usually for better remuneration and/or living conditions (Merriam Webster Dictionary, 2010). Brain drain is usually considered an economic cost on the part of the releasing countries. This is because migrants usually take with them the fraction of value of their training sponsored by governments or other organizations. It could be likened to capital flight which refers to the same movement of financial capital. The converse of brain drain is brain gain. Thus, whilst developing countries from which trained personnel are migrating are suffering from brain drain, developed nations are experiencing brain gain.

Economic Development

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Historically, economic development and growth became a concern of the so-called developed countries, with the notion that ‘poverty anywhere is a threat to prosperity everywhere’, besides, it has been an arrow of the concerned-countries’ leaders, in bid of breaking off the yoke of vicious cycle of poverty on their citizens which was not a flickering fire as it is today. Universally, economists unanimously agreed that economic development bring about reduction and/ or elimination of poverty, inequality and unemployment. Succinctly, it is noted that economic development should not be confused with economic growth. This is because, economic growth is easily quantified and measured, while economic development is more qualitative and “has meant all things to all men and women” (Arndt 1987). Economic development is focused on quality improvements, risk mitigation, innovation, and entrepreneurship that place the economy of a higher growth trajectory. While economic growth is tied to macroeconomic conditions and a function of market forces then, economic development represents the conditions that determine the microeconomic functioning of the economy, affecting both the quality of inputs and the opportunity set for firms. Economic development is associated with institutions, social capital, labor and capital mobility, and

income and wealth equity (Fagerberg, et al, 2013). Economic development is predicated on long-term investments in the generation, dissemination and absorption of new ideas, as well as infrastructure. Economic development requires collective action and large-scale investments with long time horizons. Infrastructure projects, a traditional concern of economic development, now extends to the digital realm. The standard of literacy is expanded at a time when labor force participation requires a bachelor’s degree with the expectation of continued lifetime education and training. Economic development is predicated on cooperation between the public sector and private enterprise but is defined by conditions established by government and public investments. Though it is certainly possible to have growth without development in the short or even medium-term, economic development creates the conditions that enable long-run economic growth (Feldman, et al, 2016).

More succinctly, Jhingan (1997), remarked that “economic development” refers to the problems of underdeveloped countries and economic growth to those of developing countries”. Economic development is obviously concerned with the measures to improve the social welfare of the people. In other words, these problems prevailing in less developed countries (LDCs)

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gained relevance in the literature of economic development as illustrated by (Udabah, 1999). It implied that the less developed countries are often characterized by the following conditions: poverty, little or no savings, high rates of population growth, inflation, unemployment, low rate of adult literacy, low income per capita, low standard of living, low level of technology, etc.

Subsequently, economic development is generally defined to include improvement in material welfare, especially for persons with the lowest incomes, the eradication of mass poverty with its correlates of illiteracy, disease and early death, changes in the composition of input and output that generally include shifts in the underlying structure of production away from agricultural towards industrial activities. The organization of the economy in such a way that productive employment is general among working age population rather than the situation of privileged minority and correspondingly greater participation of broad based groups in making decision about the direction, economic and otherwise, in which they should move their welfare. The economies of development refer to the problems of the economic development of underdeveloped countries (Jhingan 1997 cited in Obinwanne, 2019).

It further indicates that there are conditions or variables that determine the sequences on the economic development with reference to human capital development. Thus, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) designed the Human Development Index (HDI) to assess, measure and evaluate the trends of development in industrialized and neo-capitalist economies in the world (Okafor and Madubuegwu, 2015). In this vein, Emes, and Hahn (2001) succinctly noted that: The Human Capital Index is composed of four Human indicators in three sub-indices, life expectancy, education and Gross Domestic Product (GDP), which are averaged to arrive at the Human Development Index score. Each indicator value is computed according to the general formula:

$$\text{Indicator Value} = \frac{(\text{Country Value} - \text{Min. Value})}{(\text{Max. Value} - \text{Min. Value})}$$

Where “Country Value” is the value observed for the country of interest, and the minimum and maximum values is the result of assumptions made by the United Nations about each indicator in each sub-index. Subsequently, the sub-indicator and indices which include life-expectancy, education, income distribution, and health are the imperatives of economic development (Okafor and Madubuegwu, 2015). This assertion invariably underlines the

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significance of human capital in economic development.

Human Capital in Economic Development

Education and health are basic objectives of development. They are important ends in themselves. Health is central to well-being and education is essential for a satisfying and rewarding life; both are fundamental to broader notion of expanded human capabilities that lie at the heart of the meaning of development. Education play a key role in the ability of a developing country to absorb modern technology and to develop the capacity for self-sustaining growth and development. Moreover, health is a prerequisite for increases in productivity, and successful education relies on adequate health as well. Thus, both health and education can also be seen as vital components of growth and development as inputs to the aggregate production function. Their dual role as both inputs and outputs gives health and education their central importance in economic development (Todaro and Smith, 2011).

Succinctly, it is hard to overstate how truly dramatic the improvements in world health and education have been. In 1950, some 280 of every 1,000 children in the developing world as a whole died before their fifth birthday. By 2008, that number had fallen to 118 per 1, 000 in low-income countries (though compare with 7

percent 1,000 in high income countries and just 4 in many European countries). In addition, recent decades have witnessed a historically unprecedented extension of literacy and other basic education to a majority of people in the developing world. The United Nations reports that although there were still a staggering 780 million illiterate people aged 15 or older in the world in 2004, the good news is that 82% of all people are literate today, compared to just 63% as recently as 1970 (Selma, 2009).

Despite such outstanding achievements, developing countries continue to face great challenges as they seek to continue to improve the health and education of their people. The distribution of health and education within countries to face great challenges as they seek to continue to improve the health and education of their people. The distribution of health and education within countries is as important as income distribution; life expectancy may be quite high for better-off people in developing countries but far lower for the poor. Child mortality rates in developing countries remain more than ten times higher than those found in the rich countries. These deaths generally result from conditions that are easily treatable, including millions who continue to die needless each year from dehydration caused by diarrhea. If child death rates in developing countries fell to those

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prevailing in the developed countries, the lives of more than 8 million children would be saved each year. Many children who survive nonetheless suffer chronic problems of malnutrition, debilitating parasitic infections, and other recurrent illness. Problems caused by lack of key micronutrients such as iodine, as well as protein, affect nearly 2 billion people, but children are particularly vulnerable. Whereas a child in Europe, North America, or Japan can expect to receive more than 12 years of schooling, the average child in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia can expect to spend less than five years in school-before taking account of teacher absenteeism and making no adjustment for the lack of schoolbooks and other resources even when a teacher is present (Todaro and Smith, 2011).

Emphatically, health and education are closely related in economic development. On one hand, greater health capital may improve the return to investments in education, in part because health is an important factor in school attendance and in the formal learning process of a child. A longer life raises the return to investments in education, better health at any point during working life may in effect lower the rate of depreciation of education capital. On the other hand, greater education capital may improve the return to investments in health, because many health

programs rely on basic skills often learned at school, including personal hygiene and sanitation, not to mention basic literacy and numeracy; education is also needed for the formation and training of health personnel. Finally, an improvement in productive efficiency from investments in education raises the return on a lifesaving investment in health (Mushkin, 2011).

The foregoing analyses accentuate the imperatives of health and education as critical variables in human capital development and growth of the economy. Unfortunately as observed the flight of skilled labour in these sectors has over the decades eroded lofty ideals of economic development.

Human Capital Flight and Crisis of Economic Development in Health and Education

Sectors of Nigeria

Basically in the literature of economic development, health and education are key components of human capital and contributors to social welfare. One index of human welfare which incorporates income, education and health showed that Africa's level of 'human development' is the lowest of any region in the world (Appleton and Teal, 2008). Sadly, the flight of skilled labour in these two critical sectors of the economy (education and health)

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remains a major concern in developing countries like Nigeria in particular. Furthermore, developing countries already have poor human development indices, and further migration of human resources will continue to suppress the country (Ita, 2020). Although, it is true that economically, the country is harsh, however, the trend by the youths rushing to leave Nigeria goes beyond this singular reason (Komolafe, 2002; Amrevurayire and Ojeh, 2016; Akanle et al, 2019; Okunade, 2019). In specific sense to the prevailing unpleasant situations in critical sectors of economic development (health and education), Atteh (2020) document that the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2016 reported a shortage of 4.3 million healthcare workers worldwide. Sub-Saharan African countries (which Nigeria falls under) is the most affected by this shortage, given that they contain 3% of the world's health workers but are burdened by 24% of the global disease (WHO, 2016). Even with this reported shortage, Nigerian healthcare practitioners have continued to migrate in large numbers to other countries. It is estimated that over two million Nigerians currently reside in the United States, of which 20,000 are doctors and more than 10,000 are academics (Ogbu, 2019). Notably, according to the president of the Nigerian Medical Association during a press conference in 2021,

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that from 71, 740 doctors trained in Nigeria (as of 2019) that only 27,000 are presently practicing here. By implication, there are more Nigerian doctors (62.4%) practicing abroad than practicing practitioners (37.6%) in Nigeria. More revealing, Etuk, e tal (2023, p.18) indicated that World Health Organization recommends 1:600 doctor to patients ratio.

Furthermore, the brain drain phenomena is also felt in the space of public tertiary institutions where academics relocate from Nigeria to different parts of Europe and United States. Most of these migrating academics with PhDs in different areas of disciplines and specializations (Udono and Ufeifia, 2020). In addition, Ayodele (2022) opined that the leadership of the Academic Staff Union of Universities lamented that Nigerian university system has lost over a thousand Nigerian academics to tertiary institutions in Europe while thousands of post-doctoral fellow are seen working in various institutions of learning. In a similar sense, a total of 128, 770 Nigerian students enrolled in universities in the United Kingdom between 2015 to the end of 2022, analysis of the data obtained revealed that in 2015/2016 academic year, 16, 100 Nigerians were enrolled in UK universities. In 2016/2017 session, there was a sharp decline as only 12, 655 Nigerians enrolled while in 2018/2019 academic session, the

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number of Nigerian students reduced to 10, 685 while it rose marginally to 10, 810 during the 2018/2019 academic session. A total of 13, 020 students were enrolled during the 2019/2020 academic session while 21, 305 were enrolled during the 2020/2021 session representing a 64 percent increase. Lastly in 2021/2022 academic session, 44, 195 Nigeria students enrolled marking the highest since 1960 (Higher Education Statistics Agency, 2024).

Nigeria as a country has been grappling with challenges of economic development. These economic development problems include low standard of living, low rates of literacy, unemployment (Udech, 2019). However, the effects of flight of human capital on economic development has been a discourse of polemics. In this vein, human capital flight has a huge effect on the sourced country, yet there exist few empirical studies on such phenomenon. It is important to note that from the few empirical studies that considered the effect of working environment on human capital flight, none has been carried out to assess its effect on a developing economy like Nigeria (Etuk, e tal, 2023). Similarly, Onwunyi, e tal, (2020) documents that massive loss of human capital bedeviling Nigeria has become a source of worry and a cog in the wheel of development of the country. According to the Report of United

Nations (1998), the greatest challenge facing Nigeria as it concerns development emanate from the effect of human capital flight. Human capital flight no doubt has financial, institutional and societal cost which Nigeria is today paying for (Ezeh, 2008). From the financial front, most of the resources that were expended in the cause of training these migrated professionals constitute large financial losses to Nigeria. This is because their services are no longer channeled to Nigeria's development and social needs. On the other hand, most Nigeria's social institutions now rely on expatriates since they have all lost the indigenous competent hands due to human capital flight. The cost of recruiting and sustaining these expatriates in Nigeria as alternative manpower are usually too excruciating due to financial depletion of Nigeria mostly occasioned by the fluctuations of oil prices. This has become a serious problem to Nigerian development as resources are annually expended in the training of professionals who will within few years of gaining expertise migrate to other countries leaving its home country to suffer human capital loses. Also, Oluyemi, e tal (2021) remarked that human capital flight in critical sectors such as health and education is even more detrimental to the growth and development of African economies. This is because the region is capital-

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scarce and continuous migration of highly skilled personnel may mean financial loss for the region. As a result, the study of human capital flight in Africa nay Nigeria deserves critical attention. Continuous migration of skilled labor out of Nigeria is viewed as worrisome. This is because unemployment, rising poverty, inequality among other socio-economic challenges characterize the Nigerian economy. Interestingly, some other scholars Ulasi, (2016), Okon (2018) and Egbo (2020) have respectively argued that human capital flight has positive impacts on the economy with reference to capital remittance towards social development. A major argument for migration is remittances from abroad. World Bank, (2016) further revealed that Nigeria is the top remittance-receiving country in Africa and fifth in the world. However, the direct impact of migration on economic development is an area not very much studied in the literature (Oluyemi, e tal, 2021).

In regards to the factors underlying human capital flight, Ogunode and Ishaya (2022), argued that poor salary is one of the key causes of brain-drain problem in the Nigerian higher institutions. The monthly salaries that academic staff are receiving is less compare to what other academic staff are been paid in other countries across the World. The inability of the government to adequately fund the various

higher institutions in the country is responsible for the poor salaries and other financial benefits given to academic staff in the Nigerian higher institutions. Other factors responsible for the low salaries include corruption, fall in oil revenue and other sectors in the economy like security, health and infrastructural facilities. In the same trend, Anna (2017), also stressed that poor salary is the cause of flight of Nigeria professionals to other countries of the world.

Furthermore, in reference to remuneration and brain drain among health care practitioners, it is argued that differentials in wages between rich and poor countries offer a pull towards the developed nations (Agba & Ushie, 2013; Agba, et al., 2013; Attah & Angioha, 2019). Tessema (2010) maintained that, health personnel feel that salaries they earn abroad cannot be matched with those earned locally. Tessema points out that highly skilled health personnel who have migrated to developed countries are lured mainly by higher salaries and entitlements. Kiraya (2000) and Tessema (2010) posit that wage differentials is a major cause of brain drain. Also, Khwaja and Scaramozzino (2003) acknowledged that an important explanation for brain drain in the healthcare sector lies largely on the wage gaps between technologically advanced countries and unindustrialized countries. As a result of poor

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economic situation in developing nations, most professionals are paid wages that are considerably lower than that of their colleagues in developed nations. Professionals in developing nations, especially Africa, only manage to make a living from paltry wages they earn and a lot more live below poverty contour. Dimaya, et al (2012) asserts that, in the health sector, higher wages, better employment opportunities and technologies in industrialized nations motivate health care professionals in developing nations to migrate. More illustratively, Kiraya (2000) studied brain drain among Zambian health workers and asserts that nurses receive an average monthly remuneration of 1.1 million Kwacha (US\$ 229), clinical officials receive a salary of 1.1 million Kwacha (US\$ 229). The remunerations as identified by Lusale (2007) includes “monthly salary, regular uniform and night allowances paid as composite every month. In comparison with other governmental staff like pharmacists, technologists, environmental health technologists, and radiographers with similar duration of training, the salaries can be seen to be reasonable”. However, they are low when compared with the monthly food basket requirements estimated to be in the range of 1.4 million Kwacha (US\$ 350) for a family of six (6), and cannot cater for decent housing,

transportation, and other basic amenities such as water and electricity (Awases, et al, & Chatora, 2004; Hamada, et al & Hanson, 2009). According to this, low wages are significant to the migration of medical personnel to where remunerations are better. Padarath and Chamberlain (2003) in their article “health personnel in sub-Southern Africa: Confronted with mal-distribution and brain drain”, points that remuneration levels are potentially the most influential factors in brain drain among health workers.

Subsequently, inadequacy and deplorable learning and clinical facilities as widely seen across states of the federation impelled many to leave the country for industrialized economies where these facilities are adequate and functional. In reference to the unpleasant development, scholars and practitioners have remarked that unconducive working environment is another major factors responsible for massive movement of academic staff from the higher institution in the country to other part of the world. The working environment constitutes in majorities higher institutions in Nigeria is not conducive for effective service delivery. The working policies, administrative bottleneck, leaderships, quality of supportive services like internet facilities, light and academic freedom is not encouraging in

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motivating professional to stay and develop their career (Ogunode and Ishaya, 2022). Subsequently, Ogunode (2020) noted that factors responsible for brain-drain in the Nigerian public universities include; uncondusive working environment, poor motivation, insecurity, underfunding and political interferences. The implication of brain-drain in the Nigerian public universities include; shortage of lecturers, poor quality of education and high student-teacher ratio. In reference to health perspective, Agba (2020) remarked that deplorable working facilities have contributed to brain drain among health practitioners in Nigeria. It is further revealed that United States, United Kingdom, and Australia provide good infrastructures, and funding in their health system, unlike developing nations where these facilities are near absence (Agba & Ushie, 2010; Carvantes & Dominique 2002; Meyer & Brain, 1999; Ukwayi, e tal, 2018; Agba, e tal, 2016). This problem according to Hall (2005) are largely responsible for brain drain among medical practitioners. Ikenwilo (2007) asserts that the issue of inadequate facilities is a common feature of most developing nations. These inadequacies most times push medical practitioners to move to countries where these facilities are available. Manongi, e Tal (2006) maintained that lack of

laboratory facilities and funds to support innovation accords for brain drain.

Also, inadequate infrastructural facilities are another major factor causing brain-drain in the higher education system in Nigeria. Accordingly, Ogunode & Agwor (2021) indicated that school infrastructural facilities refer to social capital within the school environment. They include school buildings/complexes such as classrooms, tables, exam hall, chairs, auditoria, desks, staff offices, seminar/conference/board rooms, laboratories, workshops, studios, farms, gymnasia, central libraries, specialized/professional libraries, faculty libraries, departmental libraries, etc., Institute/centers', specialized facilities e.g. ICT infrastructure, special laboratories, conference facilities, etc., and Boards e.g. interactive, magnetic, screen and chalk, etc., ICT that is computer laboratories and services, network connectivity, multi-media system, public address system, slide, and video projectors, and Ergonomics furnishing in laboratories, libraries, and lecture rooms/theaters, moot courts, and studios, etc. Students' hotels or accommodation include Boys and Girls hostels; municipal/physical infrastructure i.e. power supply, water supply, good road networks. Sports, health and sanitation, staff schools,

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security facilities, etc. In this vein, Ogunode & Agwor (2021) further outlined the importance of infrastructural facilities in educational institutions include: it aids effective delivery of administrative functions in schools; It makes the delivery of services fast and reliable; It enable teachers to deliver lessons fast; Infrastructural facilities provide a conducive working environment for both teachers and students; Infrastructural facilities enable learners to learn at ease and learn well; and Infrastructural facilities enable the teachers to teach well, prepare their lessons, and deliver them online (ICT). It is unfortunate that as important as the infrastructural facilities to support effective services delivery that many public higher institutions in the country do not have the adequate. In this vein, Abdul (2013) observed that, in many higher institutions in the country, academic and non-adequate staff do not have offices. Some non-academic staff seat under the trees, move from office to office to while away time. Four to five academic staff share offices meant for two lecturers. Again, Ogunode, e tal (2021) observed that many academic staff share offices and some do not even have while many non-teaching staff seat under the trees and roam about from one office to the other because they don't have office to sit. Many academic staff do not have constant light in their offices and

internet services to support their online teaching programmer. Also, NOUN (2009) submitted that the office accommodation is inadequate in all tertiary institutions. About three to four lecturers share offices in some of the institutions (some of which are prefabricated buildings). The offices are not comfortable, and hence hinder effective performance of staff, especially the teaching (academic) staff. Ishere and Ogunode (2021) identified inadequate funding, corruption, increase in population, poor infrastructural planning, poor maintenance culture and uncompleted projects as the causes of shortage of inadequate infrastructural facilities in Nigerian public universities.

These unpleasant developments are unfortunately attributed to poor funding. A reference point to this what was seen and observed at the tertiary institutions. Also, Ogunode and Abubakar, (2020) observed that the budgetary allocation for the administration of public universities in Nigeria is not adequate to implement the programmer of universities in Nigeria. The university system requires a lot of funds for effective administration to be able realized it goals. The annual budgetary allocation for the administration of universities in Nigeria is grossly inadequate. The inability of the federal

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government to stick to the UNESCO 26% of national budget for education is affecting the management of Nigerian universities. Many higher institutions administrators in Nigeria do not have adequate funds to procure and purchase the educational resources to adequately implement the higher institutions. Due to poor funding, salaries are not paid until, infrastructural facilities are not adequate and benefits of academic staff are not paid. Ogunode (2021) observed that the implications of underfunding of the public universities include; inadequate infrastructural facilities, shortage of academic staff, poor quality of education, strike action and brain-drain.

Perhaps this ambition may have been stimulated by harsh socio-economic realities in the host countries which reflect the factuality of some of the challenges enumerated in the questionnaires. Oyowe, (1996), documents that economic problems which can cause migration of highly professionals from developing countries include poor salaries, lack of job opportunities, unemployment, inflation etc. A skilled worker decides to move from his home country for another in search for better economic conditions such as job satisfaction, a higher standard of living, better salary and educational progressive society, etc. It is a historical fact that countries which provide these “pull factors”

have welcomed the highest population of skilled migrants and these have, in reverse, made substantial efforts and contributions, not only to the economic advancement of their host nations, but also to the technological and scientific development of the world. Globally, the free movement and easily interaction of highly professionals and experts is a positive thing. But attendant cost to the home nations of losing their highly skilled professionals is incalculable in terms of both development opportunities and loss of investment. In other words, Oyede (2019), asserted that flight of highly skilled professionals in health related issues to other countries has undermined services and created chaos of uncertainties and fatalities in public hospitals. Again, there have been cases of enormous plights of patients looking forward for the indulgence of consultants for treatment.

Consequently, Nwadike (2018) posit that the flight of high-profile consultants to other countries has over the years and decades affected the morale and drive of many resident doctors and health workers across tertiary, secondary and primary health institutions in Nigeria. This unpleasant development has terribly affected the much anticipated output in clinical and sundry health services offered to our people. It is a national problem that requires adequate

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attention and effective strategic plan to tackle for the health safety of Nigerians. Despite shortfall in health personnel, many still believed that low morale among practitioners in our hospitals and poor medical attention which often result to fatalities and death can be attributed to other factors not necessarily gaps created by the flight of health workers to other developed countries of the world.

Furthermore, Ogunode and Atobauka (2022) noted that shortage of academic staff is responsible for the acute shortage of academic staff in many higher institutions in Nigeria. The Report of NEEDS (2014) submitted that the data available on teacher' shortage revealed that at the Colleges of education, 95 public colleges of education with population of students of 338,237 and teaching staff of 15,344 and teacher-students ratio of 1:22. For Polytechnics, there 45 public polytechnics with students enrolment of 166,121 and teaching staff of 5,636 while there are 37,504 teachers in the nation's public universities with a student enrolment of 1,252,913, representing a teacher-to-student ratio of 1:33. To add, Ogunode and Adamu (2021) identified brain-drain, inadequate funding, lack of strategic manpower planning, poor motivation, uncondusive working environment and corruption as the reasons for shortage of

academic staff in the Nigerian higher institutions.

In credence, Okoli, e tal (2016) and Okebukola (2002) observed that, there is diminishing scope of mentoring junior researchers by seasoned and senior researchers due to brain drain. Poor research development in many higher institutions in Nigeria is as a result of limited academic staff with experiences in carrying out research. Research is one of the key programmer of higher institutions. Research is one major indicators used for ranking higher institutions performance. Conducting quality research demands experiences researchers and academician. It is unfortunate that many higher institutions in the country do have these qualified researchers and professors due to brain drain problems. Subsequently, the mass movement of highly skilled and seasoned academics from Nigeria s tertiary institutions (particularly universities) to overseas countries for greener pasture has certainly adversely affected the quality of outputs from the institutions (Emeghara, 2019). As Yesufu (1996) aptly observes the quality of graduates is so poor that their impact on the national economy in terms of productivity is generally below the required standard for a developing economy Corroborating the above view, Oni (2008) avers that the mass movement of academics from the

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nations' universities to other countries has invariably taken its toll on the quality of outputs produced from the system.

Again, Akindele (2017), further remarked that tremendous reduction in the quality of skilled manpower in Nigeria's tertiary institutions, teaching hospitals and research Centres. Akin to the issue of fall in standard of education is that of reduction in the quality of skilled manpower in institutions of higher learning in Nigeria. Ipso facto, there is mass exodus of seasoned intellectuals from these institutions (especially the ivory tower) to other sectors of the economy within the country or other countries for greener pasture. It is hardly surprising, that the quality and quantity of academic staff will be considerably reduced. In this perspective, Mbanefo (2012) aptly observed that today the Nigerian university system continues to suffer from intellectual haemorrhage created by the problem of brain drain. This, according to him, is more so in the very critical fields of human medicine, pharmacy, computer science and engineering. Similarly, in the words of Adebayo (2010), it is stressed that many hospitals and research centres in Nigeria were without specialist and consultants in the 1990s, whilst many higher education institutions (HEIs) were left hollow and shallow. The clear implication of this development is that as a result of migration

of technological know - how, the economy cannot grow.

Nevertheless, professionals and stakeholders have been engaging with representatives of the government on issues to boost morale and productivity of health workers towards averting brain drain in the sector. In this vein, Otobo and Eitim (2020) argued that the failure of the federal government to address the plights of Nigeria workers emanate from lack of political will and greed. Career unions in various sectors of the economy have been consistent in seeking the attention of the government officials to look into welfare challenges of Nigeria workers but to no avail rather agreements reached were flagrantly abused and abandoned. In a similar sense, it is argued that Nigeria health professionals in their respective associations have engaged with the government at federal and state with a template of measures to be initiated to avert frequent flight of resourceful medics to foreign economies. However, there have not been concrete efforts on the part of the government to translate these measures into public policies to make health care delivery efficient enough to sustain the interests of health workers (Adeniji, 2015; Donkor, 2019).

In affinity with this view, Oke (2022), stressed that one of the challenges in the wheel of progress in tackling the plights of Academic Staff

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Union of University, ASUU was the inability of the council of vice chancellors to interface with the government on what should be done. The inability is caused by fear in view of the fact that the vice chancellors are the appointees of the government and, they may lack courage to bring effectively the attention of the government on to address problems of Nigeria university lecturers. Usman (2018), alleged that federal government failed to effectively solve the problems of university teachers because the association of vice chancellors failed to bring these demands to the attention of the government.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Human capital flight is a plague in Nigeria's economy. Its adverse effects on economic development is felt in two critical sectors-health and education. In scale of its effects, the medical institution is worst hit along which has invariably affected wellness and life expectancy. Sadly, government's failure in policy and drive to ensure conducive working environment and meaningful reward system amid other factors are conditions exacerbating brain drain in Nigeria. Despite efforts initiated, the unpleasant situation persist in alarming scale as many Nigeria professionals are immigrant passport holders looking for brighter opportunities in industrialized economies.

This unpleasant development therefore underscored the need for collective approach beyond government's clumsy efforts to mitigate the flight of Nigeria professionals to the economies of advanced countries of the world. This is further embellished in the recommendations below:

1. The government at levels of federal and state should work closely with the industrial unions of these professionals in health, education and other critical sectors to address priority needs and expectations of social welfare and conducive working environment for productivity and development of the economy.
2. The management of the public health facilities and tertiary institutions should be more creative to engage the private sector and international humanitarian agencies to respond to its statutory expectations and plights through career advancement, infrastructural development etc.
3. The fund such as Tertiary Fund designated for career development should be effectively explored to abate flight of professionals to other counties of the world.
4. The compelling need for the Federal Ministry of Labour and Productivity should develop a national policy on human capital development as long term action-plan to address

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the challenges of flight of professionals to other parts of the world.

5. Finally, the Nigeria Federal Ministry of Foreign Affairs should engage with foreign

mission through policy to discourage indiscriminate job offers and recruitment exercises for Nigeria professionals.

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